

Deliverable D4.4

Release resource and data sharing standards (accessible from the AI4Life website)

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Change Log

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
BMZ	BioImage Model Zoo
CI	Continuous Integration
D	Deliverable
DL	Deep Learning
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
ML	Machine Learning
RPCs	Remote Procedure Calls
SAM	Segment Anything Model
UI	User Interface
v	Version
WP	Work Package

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Executive summary

Deliverable 4.4 (D4.4) presents the metadata specifications developed by AI4Life for three key resources: pre-trained deep learning models, AI-ready datasets for training and validation, and related Jupyter notebooks. These specifications are essential for making bioimage AI resources FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), ensuring reproducibility, interoperability, and proper attribution. They were co-designed with the bioimage analysis community to cover major use cases in life science imaging.

The model specifications, implemented in the BioImage Model Zoo (BMZ), provide programmatic access to models via the BioImage.IO Core library, enabling integration into community partner tools. Dataset specifications (MIFA) standardise the provision of ground-truth data for training and validation, while Jupyter notebook and container descriptions facilitate sharing and discovery of workflows for training, validation, and execution. Together, these standards underpin AI4Life's mission to democratise AI for bioimage analysis, ensuring that models, data, and tools are accessible and reusable by the community.

1. Introduction

The AI4Life project, part of the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, is coordinated by Euro-BioImaging and involves ten partners, five of whom are European Research Infrastructures. The project started in September 2022 and will continue until September 2025, aiming to democratise the accessibility of state-of-the-art AI-based image analysis for life scientists. AI4Life focuses on establishing and supporting innovative services that cater to life scientists and AI method developers.

Work Package 4 (WP4) is dedicated to "Contributor Services" and supports several core objectives of AI4Life:

- Objective 1: Democratise the availability of AI-based image analysis methods as a FAIR service, accessible through the AI4Life service landscape and powered by the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) infrastructure.
- Objective 2: Establish standards for the submission, storage, and FAIR access to reference data, annotations (ground-truth), trained AI models, and trainable AI methods.
- Objective 3: Simplify the deployment, sharing, and dissemination of AI-based methods as a new developer-facing service within the BioImage Model Zoo (BMZ).

- Objective 5: Empower common image analysis platforms with AI tools.

The rapid increase in data generated in life science research has exposed the limitations of conventional desktop applications used for bioimage analysis. These tools struggle with the memory demands of high-throughput data and the complexity of AI-driven image analysis, often requiring substantial hardware and intricate software setups. Additionally, existing machine-learning model zoos tend to be inaccessible to a broader audience, requiring advanced programming and computer science knowledge. AI4Life addresses these challenges by providing community-driven metadata specifications and open software that ensure scalability, interoperability, and ease of use. The metadata specifications span both FAIR-related and technical aspects, while the open software enables direct use or integration of the growing BMZ collection with existing user-facing tools.

The designed metadata specifications ensure shared resources can realise their impact potential. The aims of the technical parts of these descriptions included transparency and a strong focus on interoperability across the ML landscape. Provided with metadata following the specified format, common utility libraries developed by the AI4Life consortium power a variety of tools and scripts, such as the AI4EOSC (<https://ai4eosc.eu/>) preview feature or model inference in community partner tools such as ilastik (<https://www.ilastik.org/>).

This Deliverable contributes to all Objectives of WP4.

2. Description of Work

2.1 Resources

AI4Life developed metadata specifications for the main resources required to make AI methods for bioimage analysis FAIR:

- Pre-trained models, including their weights, training data, and training code.
- AI-ready datasets for training and validation.
- Methods, encapsulated in Jupyter notebooks or containers.

These specifications ensure that resources are **reproducible**, **interoperable**, and **easily shareable** across community platforms. Fully specified pre-trained models include links

to their training data and training code resources, allowing creation of fully reproducible and extendable AI-based workflows.

2.2 Models

The AI4Life project develops and maintains a technical specification for a model metadata file format (<https://github.com/bioimage-io/spec-bioimage-io>) that can be used to share FAIR ML models dedicated to bioimage processing with the life sciences community, regardless of the image processing task (e.g., segmentation, denoising), model architecture (e.g., unet, transformers), training data modality (brightfield light microscopy, electron microscopy) or image processing software (e.g., ilastik, deepimagej). This format specifies the required machine-readable metadata for correctly loading, running and validating a DL model, as well as human-readable metadata that helps users find a suitable model, identify its authors, cite it properly and get basic usage instructions.

Community partner tools are encouraged to implement the specification and be able to both load and export trained models into the defined metadata format. The AI4Life consortium provides a reference implementation of this functionality in the form of a Python library (<https://github.com/bioimage-io/core-bioimage-io-python>), a command-line executable (<https://bioimage-io.github.io/core-bioimage-io-python/bioimageio/core.html>), and a Java library (<https://github.com/bioimage-io/IDL>), which can be used by partner projects to quickly achieve compliance with the standards and share the development of common algorithms and utility functions.

Models that adhere to the specification can be published and shared with the community via the Bioimage Model Zoo (<https://bioimage.io/#/models>), a user-friendly online repository of pre-trained models. These specifications allow users to search for models using the embedded FAIR metadata (name, tags, description, authors), to visually inspect the type of data used to train the models and to test run the model on user's own images (in line with the previous Deliverable 4.3). The BMZ is equipped with extensive testing and validation functionalities that verify the structure and basic deployment of submitted models. This is included in the continuous integration (CI) pipeline, as part of the BMZ backend and in coordination with the BioEngine (<https://github.com/bioimage-io/bioengine>). Those models that successfully pass the BMZ CI, are tagged with extra clarifying information regarding the quality and completeness of the model metadata and its general runtime robustness.

2.2.1 Detailed description of model specifications

The AI4Life model specification defines a “model” to be a self-contained .zip archive that complies with a special format (<https://github.com/bioimage-io/spec-bioimage-io>). The central point of the specifications is the “Resource Description”, a .yaml file named “rdf.yaml” or “bioimageio.yaml” containing the model metadata and specific references to the files within the .zip archive in a standardised manner. Together, the standardised content within the zip file enables model execution (i.e., adequately pre-processing an image, loading model weights, processing the image with the model, and running the post-processing operations), validating the model (e.g., validating the output of a given test input for black-box testing), or searching for the model within the BMZ.

The structure and fields of the Resource Description are strictly defined as part of the specification, and its creation and validation are usually performed programmatically by the community partners (e.g., biapy, CAREamics), potentially by leveraging the reference implementation provided by the bioimageio core library.

A model’s Resource Description must contain machine-readable metadata that specifies how a model is to be loaded and run. This part of the metadata is roughly composed of the following components:

- **Model weights:** References to one or more entries in the .zip archive that contain the weights of the pre-trained neural network. These weights can be in many formats, such as “Onnx” and “Torch”, and the community is encouraged to provide as many weight formats as possible to facilitate compatibility with partner tools, while reducing the usage of special features of particular weight formats. Converted weight formats for improved cross-compatibility have to mark their parent weights and are tested with the same test inputs and outputs to ensure logical equivalence.
- **Model Inputs and Outputs:** Each model has unique expectations on the data it accepts to be processed, and unique guarantees around the output that it produces. For a partner tool to correctly run a model, it must be aware of these constraints. As such, the model Resource Description specifies special fields to describe these constraints. Properties such as the shape, data type, number of inputs, and outputs are defined in the specification, with further extensions planned to expand on the semantics of the data ingested and emitted by the models.
- **Data Pre- and Postprocessing:** Often, the inputs and outputs of the neural network do not match the desired inputs and outputs of the Model Resource as a

whole. For example, it might be the case that a neural network inside a Model Resource emits output data whose shape and semantics are so bespoke to its domain that further processing by consumers of such models might become too cumbersome. To alleviate this constraint, the model Resource Description provides specifications for general data pre- and postprocessing steps, and implementations of the specification are expected to run input data first through the preprocessing steps, then through the neural network, and finally through the postprocessing steps, producing an output that is more adequate to be further processed in a user's application or data processing pipeline.

The preprocessing steps for the input can be parametrized by the dataset statistics (for example, normalization of mean and standard deviation) so that the resulting Model Resource can be applied to a wide range of input data.

Besides functional metadata, the Model Resource also specifies a rich set of FAIR metadata that helps users discover, identify, cite, or reuse those resources. Some of this metadata includes:

- **Authors:** The people responsible for the creation of this resource;
- **Cite:** The publications that should be cited when using the model to accredit original authors of a network's architecture or training data.
- **Maintainers:** The people responsible for fixing bugs in this model, as well as keeping it operational in case of changes in the infrastructure.
- **Documentation:** Human-readable instructions on how this model is to be used, its capabilities and limitations, and how to validate its performance on unseen data;
- **Description:** A concise description of the functionality and capabilities of a model, allowing one to quickly gauge relevancy.
- **Tags:** Special terms that hint at the purpose of this model to improve findability, for example, for discovery on the BMZ website;
- **Cover Images:** A visual representation of the input and output data used as part of the model card on the BMZ website. Its purpose is to enable users to quickly identify the type of data this model is meant to be applied to or which group of models it is connected to.

Finally, some metadata in the Resource Description is used for testing and validation:

- **Test Input and Output:** An example of typical input data as well as the expected output. This field is used to verify that the model behaves as expected when publishing to the Model Zoo. This is often similar or identical to the data in "Cover Images", but it is not required to have a visual representation.

- **Reproducibility or Precision Expectations:** As the model is run on different hardware and software, it is possible for the outputs to not be byte-for-byte identical to the expected test outputs. The Resource Description specification allows for determining what amount of deviation from the reference test outputs is still considered to be correct. If deviations occur, a detailed report can be generated with the bioimage.io library to inspect environment-dependent differences of reproduced outputs.
- General documentation about model format and how to contribute a model can be found here: <https://bioimage.io/docs/#/guides/developers-guide>

2.2.2 Features and benefits of model specifications

1. Storage: It enables hosting models in the zoo, which is connected to S3/Hypha/Zenodo for CI, curation and review, and uploading the model versioned with a DOI once validation has passed. The defined standard enables the programmatic interaction with this part of the infrastructure. The resource metadata information is indexed in a SQL database in the Hypha server hosted at KTH for searching and rendering on the model zoo website.

2. Access: We identify three different ways of accessing AI models

- The AI4Life project develops and maintains the Bioimage Model Zoo at <https://bioimage.io/>. The Model Zoo is an open repository for models that adhere to the aforementioned specification, where users can search for models, inspect them, run them online on sample images, and download them to be used locally.

Models that are uploaded to the zoo are automatically assigned a DOI and a URL. Additionally, models in the zoo are attributed a user-friendly nickname that is easy to remember and reference, like "affable shark", which facilitates sharing and referring to models.

- From user-friendly software & community partners tools: by adopting the specs, tool developers can enable access to models through their tools
 - How to be compatible as a community partner software:
<https://bioimage.io/docs/#/guides/community-partners-guide>
 - The AI4Life project also provides users with [a standalone graphical application](#) to open, inspect, edit and package models, which can either be run locally or on the web. This model builder GUI assists users by revealing all existing fields in the specification, with user-friendly, dynamic tooltips and real-time error reporting. It can also collapse groups of fields down to a summarized header, or hide fields that cannot be present at the same time, reducing the cognitive load of having all fields visible all the time. Model developers can build a model .zip archive from scratch or open an existing one for editing and re-exporting and be reasonably sure that the model they have created is compliant with the specification.
- From dedicated Python libraries (bioimageio.core & bioimageio.spec)

3. Sharing: Models are openly shared with the community through the BioImage Model zoo website, with the model weights license specified in the required metadata.

4. Interoperability between community partners: Community partners, i.e., software tools that adopted our standards, enjoy guaranteed compatibility between initiatives that would otherwise be separated by incompatible formats.

- <https://github.com/bioimage-io/collection?tab=readme-ov-file#add-community-partner>
- Hypha API <https://bioimage.io/#/api?tab=hypha-rpc>

Shared resources can be evaluated for their compatibility with registered partner tools. The compatibility reports are gathered and displayed alongside them on the BMZ website.

Independent of the BMZ website, the common standard and the interoperability derived from it allow the utilization and combination of multiple tools in a given project to create workflows that otherwise could only emerge through individual, dedicated development efforts.

2.3 Data

There exist two standards to describe datasets in AI4Life:

Bioimage.io data description: A standard to attach plain metadata to publicly available datasets, for a human to discover what is there. The Dataset Descriptions also facilitate linking other shared bioimage.io Resource Descriptions to publicly available datasets. In particular, this standardizes how Model Descriptions can reference the data their network was trained on.

Biolmage Archive: Standards for annotated data to be hosted in dedicated, publicly available cloud resources (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/about/teams/bioimage-archive/>). These have mostly been described elsewhere: for images, we use the widely adopted REMBI guidelines:

- Paper: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41592-021-01166-8>
- Model reference for our implementation: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/bioimage-archive/rembi-model-reference/>
- Repo with our implementation: <https://github.com/Biolmage-Archive/bia-rembi-models>

For image annotations, we use the MIFA standard, developed by the AI4Life consortium in consultation with the wider community:

- Paper (in press in Nature Methods): <https://arxiv.org/abs/2311.10443>
- Model reference for our implementation: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/bioimage-archive/mifa-model-reference/>
- Repo with our implementation: <https://github.com/Biolmage-Archive/bia-mifa-models>

Further development plans include the representation of Biolmage Archive datasets following the MIFA standard on the [bioimage.io](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/bioimage-io/) website using the bioimage.io Dataset Descriptions. The two metadata standards complement each other, as all required metadata to programmatically create the bioimage.io Dataset Descriptions is available in the MIFA standard.

2.4 Other resources

Notebooks and applications: Similar to the plain bioimage.io Dataset Description, the bioimage.io notebook specification describes what FAIR metadata to attach to notebooks and applications.

Unlike the Model Description, the notebook and application standards do not directly

facilitate validating their functionality programmatically due to a wide range of usage scenarios. However, the standard allows users to find notebooks and applications in a structured manner, gives community members an overview of available tools and shows how they link to published Model Descriptions.

Furthermore, it encourages good scientific practice by making referencing these resources easy and providing guidance on how to cite them.

Containers: Synchronised with the Deliverable 4.2–deployment of a container system–, we created the specifications to containerise, publish and access reproducible AI pipelines following FAIR principles using Docker containers (<https://github.com/HenriquesLab/DL4MicEverywhere/blob/main/docs/FORMAT.md>).

These specifications consider the requirements needed to recreate Python environments–with and without GPU – across operating systems (i.e., Linux, Mac and Windows) and implement a standard name and version convention for the corresponding Docker Image. This way, users can access the exact environment reported by model developers to deploy their AI pipelines, regardless of their hardware resources.

To ease the creation and launching of containerised pipelines, and ensure their traceability and accessibility in the long term, for both experts and non-expert users, we developed DL4MicEverywhere (<https://github.com/HenriquesLab/DL4MicEverywhere>). By contributing a pipeline to the DL4MicEverywhere platform, developers can easily adopt the standards, ensure that the corresponding Docker Image is adequately built and published in Docker Hub, and make the pipeline accessible through the BMZ website.

3. Conclusion

With this Deliverable, AI4Life established specifications for sharing pre-trained models, AI-ready datasets and related Jupyter notebooks on the BMZ website and – for datasets – on the BiImage Archive. Pre-trained model metadata allows for standardised programmatic access to the BMZ model resources, enabling community partner tools to run many external models and thus deliver substantial additional value to their users in the bioimaging community. Similarly, this metadata specification enables algorithm developers to make their models accessible to users of all the partner tools without any additional adjustment. Furthermore, AI4Life proposed metadata standards for AI-ready training and validation data (MIFA) in the BiImage Archive and for notebooks used for training, finetuning, validation and execution of models, making these important resources FAIR for developers and for users. Our standards have been driven by

community use cases, encapsulating the most important metadata across imaging modalities, analysis tasks and model architectures.

Looking ahead, the AI4Life standards will be maintained and further extended through continued engagement with the bioimage analysis community.

